

Research Methodology for Technological Innovations in Costume Practice (TICP): A Science and Technology Studies Informed Qualitative Investigation

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1. Overview of the research project and this document

The production of stage costumes relies on the talents and expertise of diverse costume professionals. These practitioners employ a range of tools and technologies as they collaboratively convert costume ideas or 2D sketches into 3D garments and accessories. Industry 4.0 manufacturing technologies, such as digital patternmaking and 3D printing (the two technologies this research uses methodologically as examples), offer substantial benefits for costume construction in terms of productivity, financial savings, sustainability, and creativity. Yet, the adoption of such technologies is haphazard and hindered by perceptions that costume practice is not technically innovative. This perception is informed by systematic gender biases that limit investment in and recognition of the skills and creativity of costume professionals, who are predominantly female.

Technological Innovations in Costume Practice (TICP) is a research justice project that uses theories about sociotechnical change to investigate the integration of technological innovations, specifically digital patternmaking and 3D printing, in the work of costume professionals. It aims to develop theoretical models and practical resources to facilitate technology adoption. The questions guiding the research project are, first, *what structural and attitudinal factors constrain and facilitate technology adoption in costume practice, and what are the impacts and implications of such adoption?* And secondly: *What resources do costume practitioners need to support their adoption of these tools?* The research draws on theories of sociotechnical change, specifically domestication theory (Silverstone and Haddon 1996; Landmark et al. 2024) and diffusion of innovations theory (Rogers 2003). The project will develop academic knowledge and resources for the adoption of technology in costume that respond to its particular context and operations. Such outcomes will enable practitioners to be more deliberate, effective and empowered when engaging with new manufacturing technologies. To deliver these outcomes, the project has two primary data collection phases and combines data from three sources: interviews, site visits of costume workrooms and co-design workshops.

This methodology reporting document is intended to fulfil EU Open Science requirements by providing detailed protocols enabling research replication. By detailing the protocols for data collection, processing, and analysis, as well as the specific qualitative methods implemented, and the research's ethical and procedural aspects, transparency and repeatability are ensured, allowing for context and timing. While the data collected in the study are not available due to GDPR restrictions, this documentation and appended research instruments provide the necessary information to convey the research process. This document draws on Aguinis and Solarino (2019) recommendations to address key areas, including research design, positionality, participant interaction, challenges encountered, and future recommendations.

2. Research Setting: The Live Performance Costume Industry

The TICP project situated itself within the professional live performance costume industry, a globally distributed but structurally interconnected field characterised by distinctive operational hierarchies, economic precarity, and deeply gendered labour practices. Understanding these contextual conditions was essential to interpreting how costume practitioners engage with

technological innovation, as adoption decisions are inseparable from the material and institutional structures constraining costume work.

The live performance industry operates within rigid hierarchical power structures that shape costume work fundamentally (Taylor 2025a). Production hierarchies position costume departments subordinate to broader technical and creative leadership, with costume typically reporting to technical directors or production managers—roles traditionally occupied by individuals from non-costume backgrounds who may lack understanding of costume-specific workflows or constraints (Taylor, 2025b). These hierarchies directly influence technology adoption: decisions about equipment investment, training resources, and workflow integration frequently bypass costume practitioners themselves and rest with managers who may not understand costume manufacturing processes intimately. Relatedly, costume is frequently positioned as anachronistic—reliant on "traditional" hand skills and familiar mechanical sewing machines—despite its sophisticated, collaborative, and technical dimensions.

Within costume workshops, labour is typically stratified: lead costume makers or heads of department exercise authority over pattern cutters, machinists, and assistants, with authority often determined by experience, skill, or tenure rather than formal qualifications. Relatedly, employment conditions significantly shape the possibilities for adoption. The costume workforce is characterised by substantial precarity: many practitioners, particularly pattern cutters and specialist machinists, work on freelance or contract bases tied to individual productions, creating job insecurity that shapes responses to labour-displacing technologies. As noted in the TICP application, precariously employed practitioners have explicitly raised concerns about technologies threatening employment, whereas permanently employed staff may view adoption differently (Sbrizzi et al., 2022). This precarity intersects directly with gender: approximately 80 per cent of costume professionals are female, and the field is subject to a documented gender wage gap relative to other male-dominated technical disciplines (Essin, 2021; Kodicek, 2022). However, this precarity and casual employment also enable the movement of people and knowledge between workplaces, and this learning and constant development is seen as one of the intrinsic benefits of the profession.

Economically, costume production is labour and time intensive. Theatre companies, especially publicly funded institutions, frequently operate within budget constraints. This means costume departments often operate with aging equipment, limited training opportunities, and skeleton staffing, creating conditions in which adopting new technology requires substantial upfront investment with unclear returns. Costume workshops themselves function within specific spatial and temporal norms: production timelines are rigid and non-negotiable, dictated by performance schedules, and costume work must integrate within these fixed windows. Workshops are typically designed around sewing machinery and hand-work stations, with spatial configurations reflecting established practices. The introduction of digital fabrication technologies (3D printers, digital patternmaking software) requires physical space, technical infrastructure such as higher-quality computers, software subscriptions, internet connections, and other equipment, and workflow reorganisation that existing workshops may not easily accommodate.

Culturally, costume practice is shaped by professional values positioning costume as subordinate to narrative and character: the profession's stated goal is often to "recede" in favour of story, creating a cultural framework where invisibility is valued (Bruzzi 1995; Monks 2015).

This discourse reflects and perpetuates systematic undervaluation of feminised labour (Taylor, 2025a). Understanding these intersecting power structures, economic constraints, employment precarity, and cultural devaluations was fundamental to TICP's analytical approach, enabling the project to examine technology adoption not as an individual choice but as a negotiation within complex institutional, material, and gendered contexts.

3. Research Design

To examine the structural and attitudinal factors that constrain and facilitate the incorporation of new manufacturing technologies into professional costume practice, this research combines qualitative data collection with theories about sociotechnical change, specifically domestication and innovation diffusion theories.

Domestication theory considers both the symbolic and practical aspects of adopting new technologies, such as emerging meanings or changes to routines and examines the role of users in innovation (Silverstone and Haddon 1996, Landmark et al. 2024). Similarly, Rogers' well-regarded diffusion theory addresses the elements of influence (the innovation itself, adopters, communication channels, time, and surrounding social system) and the process of decision-making (awareness, interest, evaluation, trial, and adoption) (Rogers 2003). These two theories inform the research design, including data collection instruments, coding, and analysis, and when combined with costume and theatre production theory, also the model development. Integrating the two disciplinary perspectives of costume and sociology, specifically technology and innovation studies, enables original research, rigour, and the potential transferability of findings.

To address the study's research questions, being firstly: *What structural and attitudinal factors constrain and facilitate technology adoption in costume practice, and what are the impacts and implications of such adoptions?* and secondly: *What resources do costume practitioners need to support their adoption of these tools?*, the study combines data from three sources: interviews, ethnography and co-design workshops. The overall research design is diagrammed in Figure 1 and expanded on below.

Figure 1: Technological Innovations in Costume Practice Research Design

3.1. Interviews

To collect data on the factors influencing how costume practitioners engage with new manufacturing technologies, semi-structured interviews (approximately 1-1.5 hours each) with international costume professionals were conducted. Interviewees were selected due to their experience with the technologies under investigation, with a mix of 'early adopters' already using the technologies and 'early majority' adopters who are newer users interviewed. The interviews were carried out via Zoom, and audio and video recorded. The sub-questions guiding these interviews were:

- What do practitioners perceive as the productivity, financial, sustainability and creativity benefits of the technology's adoption?
- What barriers are encountered in adoption and how are these navigated?
- What encourages or enables adoption?

Narrative interview questions uncovered symbolic meanings and implicit knowledge (Anderson and Kirkpatrick 2016), questions using domestication theory frames allowed comparison across participants, and 'virtual site visits' or 'tours' of participants' digital workspace via screen sharing of a current or recent project elicit actual practices and processes. With additional permission, screenshots of their creative works shared on the 'virtual site' tour were taken. For a complete list of interview questions and the interview protocol, please see Appendix 4.

The research selected interviews as the primary method because they enabled the gathering of a range of in-depth perspectives directly from experienced practitioners that could not be captured through observation alone. This approach allowed for probing questions to explore specific barriers and enablers in detail. The audio-visual format helped build rapport and capture nonverbal cues throughout the data collection process.

'Virtual site visits' provided direct observation of technology use in professional contexts and elicited tacit benefits and changes regarding practices and processes. The combination of early adopters and early majority participants provided insights across the adoption spectrum.

3.2. Ethnography

To collect data on the factors influencing how costume practitioners engage with new manufacturing technologies, the research design originally planned to conduct digital ethnography. Digital ethnography (DE) is the collection of data from online social spaces (Kaur-Gill and Dutta 2017), with ethnography being a trusted and well-established innovation research method (Hoholm and Araujo 2011, Ritala, Schneider, and Michailova 2020), and the specific topic under study lending itself to digital research methods. This was planned to include observing 2-4 Facebook professional groups dedicated to costume work, collecting de-identified posts and comments discussing digital patternmaking software and 3D printing. This method was expected to provide access to naturally occurring discourse about these technologies within professional communities, revealing collective perspectives on benefits, barriers, and enablers from both users and non-users, and practitioners at various stages of technology adoption, and to allow access to a larger sample of professionals than would be possible through interviews alone. Further, the method could capture both explicit statements and implicit attitudes towards these technologies.

However, issues were encountered in gaining informed consent and ethical access to the group's data. Some groups operating publicly were observed, but the leading expected data site was inaccessible because the administrators were unresponsive to contact attempts. Due to this, and the wealth of data being collected through interviews and direct interaction, site visits and in-person ethnography were prioritised instead. This involved the researcher visiting costume workshops in several European cities, observing on-site technology use, and discussing its value with practitioners during morning teas and venue tours.

3.3. Co-design Workshops

To transform the findings into practical resources designed to help individual practitioners and companies adopt new technologies, this data collection phase presented the research findings to industry members in a series of three co-design workshops. Co-design, also known as participatory design, is a research method that offers participants or the sector under study a voice in how the findings and any outcomes are used; this method has been used in similar studies where organisations or workplaces are adopting new technologies (e.g. Bornet & Brangier 2016; Treasure-Jones et al. 2019; Salmi & Mattelmäki 2021). The question steering this phase was:

- *What resources do costume practitioners need to support their adoption of these tools?*

The in-person workshops ran for approximately 3 hours (not including catering breaks) and were aimed at costume makers, designers and related professionals. Participation involved learning about the technologies through talks and demonstrations, a presentation on the research findings, and a series of mapping, brainstorming, and critical feedback activities in small groups to explore options and priorities for the practical resources. Data collected included video recordings of workshop conversations, transcriptions of the recordings, and materials created by participants during activities (e.g. sketches/ diagrams/ notes or written comments), as well as researcher notes from the sessions.

Using co-design to answer this question enabled quick and efficient gathering of a variety of perspectives from a broader group than interviews would allow, which is essential to ensure any resources created are widely applicable. Further, compared to focus groups, co-design ensures responsiveness to industry needs and enables testing of tangible aspects of the resources.

4. Insider Positioning and Research Ethics

As a researcher, I occupied a firmly insider position within costume practice research and the broader professional costume field. This positioning emerged from my over two decades of professional experience as a costume maker and designer across over 90 productions in theatre, dance, opera, circus, contemporary performance and film, combined with fifteen years of scholarly research into costume practice and collaboration. Insider status was instrumental in shaping the TICP project's research design and in framing central questions.

My professional foundation provided intimate, embodied knowledge of the operational and institutional structures that frame costume work. This knowledge encompasses the specific production timelines that constrain decision-making in live performance; the employment arrangements and precarity that characterise much costume labour, the power hierarchies embedded within production teams and between costume departments and other technical disciplines; and the persistent gender dynamics that have historically undervalued costume work relative to other (often male-dominated) technical roles. This structural understanding allowed recognition that technological adoption cannot be examined in isolation from the material conditions of costume practice. Consequently, the research design positioned costume manufacturing technologies not simply as tools to be adopted, but as interventions within complex, gendered, and precarious labour contexts. The ability to ask research questions that accounted for employment conditions, collaborative relationships, and industry discourse emerged directly from this professional knowledge. This insider understanding enabled TICP to foreground how employment precarity shapes practitioner responses to technological change, how hierarchical structures within production teams influence access to new tools, and how gender biases in the broader performance industry intersect with discourse positioning costume as technologically static (Taylor 2025b).

The researcher's insider status, whilst facilitating access and rapport, also required conscious reflexivity to avoid projecting personal experiences onto participant narratives. Regular supervisory debriefings and presentation of the project in research group meetings provided external perspectives. Where participant accounts challenged the researcher's prior professional understandings, these dissonances were specifically flagged and explored.

4.1. Relationships with Study Participants and Access

I held pre-existing professional relationships with approximately 20% of TICP study participants, developed through attendance at international costume conferences and participation in professional organisations such as the OI STAT Costume Sub-commission. These existing relationships operated as entry points into the research and facilitated rapid trust-building with established professional contacts. However, the relationships did not intensify into close collaborative partnerships during data collection. Instead, I strategically leveraged this pre-existing professional network to facilitate access to additional participants through referrals and introductions, with approximately 30 per cent of the study cohort recruited via this mechanism. This approach allowed the extension of the participant group beyond my immediate

professional contacts to encompass practitioners across different geographic regions, employment contexts, and levels of technological adoption—including those who had adopted I4.0 technologies and those who remained sceptical or unable to access them.

My international professional positioning, whilst creating some distance from the practitioner cohort due to my academic role rather than primary practice involvement, simultaneously enabled efficient trust-building with new participants. Practitioners recognised my credibility within the field through my professional history and existing network relationships. This was most evident when my initial cold approach went unanswered by the busy professionals I sought to talk to, but a follow-up mentioning mutual colleagues or via an email introduction was successful. The international character of costume networks—where professional relationships, knowledge exchange, and collaborative projects often cut across national borders through conferences, online platforms, and international productions—meant that geographic distance between my previous working location (Australia) and the international practitioners I sought to speak to presented little barrier to participant access or relationship development. Instead, my established position within these transnational professional networks positioned me as a legitimate research partner and knowledge broker who understood the international dimensions of contemporary costume practice.

4.2. Management of Power Imbalances and Ethical Crediting

Recognising potential power imbalances inherent in the research relationships between the academic and practitioner, and between the researcher and research participant, is critical for ethical research. Whilst my professional credibility within costume networks facilitated participant trust, this exact positioning created asymmetries: I held authority in framing the research questions, determining what counted as data, and controlling the narrative through publication and dissemination. To mitigate such imbalances, the TICP project employed several mechanisms. First, recruitment communications were managed directly by me rather than through supervisory channels, and all potential participants received explicit and repeated statements of participation's voluntary nature, delivered via email to avoid interpersonal pressure that might come from synchronous communication. Second, the consent process deliberately offered participants granular control over their representation and crediting. Rather than imposing pseudonymity, participants could elect whether their contributions were credited with their name or anonymised, whether their professional experience and work location could be disclosed, and whether visual documentation of their creative work could appear in publications (see Appendix 3 and 7). This approach recognised that many participants viewed research engagement as an opportunity for professional recognition and visibility within the field, and that denying them credit could reproduce the historical undervaluing of costume labour that TICP seeks to contest. Third, the interview method itself was designed to centre participant expertise. Interviews incorporated narrative and 'virtual site visit' formats that privileged practitioners' own articulations of their work and decision-making processes, moving beyond extractive models of data collection. Following interviews, participants received a thank-you communication that offered a further opportunity to clarify or add information, positioning the researcher as accountable to participants' perspectives rather than treating the interview as a concluded transaction.

Similarly, the recruitment and crediting of co-design participants followed equivalent protocols to mitigate power imbalances. Further, in these workshops, the collaborative nature and co-learning status were emphasised, and, where feasible, I, as the researcher, set up the space to

spatially reinforce this equality, for example, by having everyone sit at one table, with no one in the “head” or power position.

Throughout data processing for data from both phases, the researcher and supervisor maintained strict access controls, with personal data stored separately from research materials and data protected by university-set safety measures. Across all dissemination activities—whether conference presentations, peer-reviewed publications, or industry-focused reports—visual materials, practice examples, and creative work shared by participants are attributed to their creators, ensuring that practitioner contributions receive sustained and visible recognition throughout the research lifecycle. These mechanisms collectively sought to position participants as collaborators in knowledge production rather than as research subjects, to acknowledge their expertise, and to maintain their agency over how their professional knowledge was represented and circulated.

4.3. Data Disclosure and Management

The TICP project prioritises participant confidentiality and consent compliance by not making raw interview or workshop materials, including transcripts and video recordings, publicly available. These raw materials contain identifiable personal data, including participant names, faces, voices, professional experiences, and creative work subject to a potential production embargo. Publishing these materials is very difficult due to GDPR restrictions. It would require extensive pseudonymisation protocols that would obscure the contextual and biographical information essential to understanding participants' professional positioning and experiences. Rather than attempting such anonymisation, which cannot be guaranteed, and which also risks rendering participants' expertise invisible, the researcher retains raw data under secure, confidential storage with restricted access, with these materials available only to authorised research personnel and, where necessary, to peer reviewers under confidentiality agreements for publication verification. The data collected in the project will be retained for up to 10 years after project completion, with final responsibility for the data transfer to Australia resting with the researcher, subject to EU/EEA Standard Contractual Clauses for data security and protection, for further scientific endeavours within and beyond the originating scientific discipline.

5. Data collection and processing

5.1. Sampling procedures

The sampling strategy was designed to capture diverse perspectives across the technology adoption spectrum, from early innovators to those encountering implementation barriers. This research employed purposive and snowball sampling procedures across three data collection methods: interviews, digital ethnography, and co-design workshops.

5.1.1. Interview Recruitment

Interview participants were recruited through a two-stage purposive sampling approach grounded in Rogers' (2003) diffusion of innovation theory. The first group consisted of early adopters of either or both technologies: 3D printing and digital patternmaking, who were already actively using these technologies in their costume practice. These participants were identified and recruited through the researcher's and supervisor's existing professional networks, conference programmes, and published or online sources in which they had discussed their

use of technology. Inclusion criteria centred on demonstrated knowledge of the technologies, availability for interview, and interest in the project. These initial interviews employed purposive, criterion-based sampling to capture practitioners with established technological expertise.

The recruitment then shifted to snowball sampling for the second group of early majority adopters. Initial interviewees were asked to recommend colleagues they had recently taught or collaborated with for the first time using the technology, or who knew about it but had not adopted it. This network-based approach enabled access to practitioners who were newer to or less embedded with the technologies, capturing different stages of the adoption process and illuminating barriers encountered during implementation. Before each interview, participants received detailed project-specific information sheets, privacy notices, and consent forms via email or social media message (See Appendices 1,2 and 3). Participants were offered opportunities to ask questions before committing to participate, and signed consent forms were collected before each interview commenced. Overall, 33 interviews were conducted.

5.1.2. Ethnography Recruitment

Digital ethnography sites were initially selected through purposive sampling based on specific criteria: length of group operation, activity level, size, and diversity. Research sites (two to four Facebook groups dedicated to costume professionals) were identified through professional network recommendations and keyword searches within the platform. Initial recruitment for non-public groups targeted group administrators through social media messages to request permission for the research. Following a lack of success with this avenue, site visits for in-person ethnography were pursued.

These were selected based on participant availability and interest (for example, several visits were carried out with interview participants), technology use, and the researcher's mobility (for example, visits to workshops were carried out at the same time as other research activities, such as conference attendance or talks).

5.1.3. Workshop Recruitment

A mix of theoretical and pragmatic sampling concerns determined workshop locations. Finland, as the site of the research and a location with a wealth of early adopters, was an obvious place to carry out the workshops. In consultation with the project supervisor, Greece was determined to be a valuable further workshop location, given its diverse workshop practices and traditions and minimal technology adoption. Once the workshop locations were selected, participants were recruited through purposive sampling via existing professional mailing lists, including the Finnish Association of Set and Costume Designers, Costume Research in Finland network, Hellenic Costume Society and direct emails to costume supervisors of local costume workshops. Potential participants were contacted through direct email or electronic flyers (see Appendix 8 as an example) distributed either by the researcher or on the researcher's behalf through list administrators. Membership in these professional networks or employment at these sites functioned as effective pre-screening, ensuring participants possessed relevant professional knowledge and interest in costume practice and technological innovation. Recruitment emails included or linked to detailed project-specific information sheets, privacy notices, and consent forms, offering participants opportunities to ask questions before committing. At the workshop commencement and prior to recording activation, participants were orally informed by the researcher about research goals and processes, and offered opportunities for questions. Hard copy consent forms were collected prior to the workshop,

with printed information sheets and privacy notices available for reference (see Appendices 5, 6 and 7).

5.2. Relative Importance of Participants

The early adopter participants held particular importance as key informants (Shaffer & Hillman, 2000) for this research. Their established experience with the case study technologies positioned them to provide rich, detailed accounts of adoption processes, practical implementation, and symbolic meanings attached to technological integration. These practitioners illuminated the facilitators of successful adoption and articulated the perceived benefits across productivity, financial sustainability, and creativity dimensions. Their role extended beyond individual cases: they functioned as bridges to the early majority participants through the snowball sampling mechanism. The early majority participants contributed crucial insights into adoption barriers and identified what resources or information might facilitate technology uptake for those less familiar or confident with technology use.

5.3. Data Collection and Processing Protocols

Data collection employed three distinct methods: semi-structured interviews with technology adopters, ethnography in professional workshops, and co-design workshops with costume practitioners. The timeline for data collection is visualised in Figure 2, which shows that interviews and site visits occurred during Phase 1 (March-November 2025), with concurrent analysis informing the design of Phase 2 co-design workshops (June-October 2025). This phased approach enabled iterative refinement, with early findings from interviews shaping workshop activities and discussion prompts.

Figure 2: Data Collection Timeline

5.3.1. Interviews

Interview data collection followed strict protocols established in the approved ethics application. Each interview session lasted between one and 1.5 hours and was conducted via Zoom, necessitating video recording to capture non-verbal communication, gestures, and screen-sharing during the digital workspace tours that formed part of the interview protocol. Between 31st March and 30 September 33 interviews were conducted, with participants from 15 countries around the world.

At the start of each interview and prior to activating recording, participants were orally reminded by the researcher about research goals and processes, and offered another opportunity to ask questions. The interview protocol employed three distinct probing techniques: narrative interview questions to reveal symbolic and cultural meanings; semi-structured questions using domestication theory frames for practical information; and screen-sharing for digital workspace tours of current or recent projects. See Appendix 4 for the full interview protocol. With explicit additional permission, screenshots of creative works shared during these tours were captured. All interviews were both video and audio recorded to preserve the richness of participant responses, with a secondary audio recording taken to ensure a backup of the data was captured.

Following each interview, participants were reminded of the researcher's contact details, and a follow-up email was sent thanking them for their time and offering another opportunity for questions. Video recordings were saved in .mp4 format, audio recordings in .mp3 or .wav format, and stored on secure Aalto IT systems with network-based backup. Transcription of the recordings was carried out on an internal Aalto AI voice-to-text transcription platform, and the transcript was then manually checked for accuracy and formatting. Aligning with GDPR requirements, any incidentally revealed special categories of personal data (such as union membership or sexual orientation) deleted during the transcription phase. Transcripts were saved as .doc files following Aalto IT recommendations for stable file formats. The transcription process maintained participant identifiability where explicit consent had been obtained, enabling analysis of correlations between professional experiences and technological adoption patterns.

5.3.2. Ethnography

The shift towards in-person workshop visits and site-based data collection meant that site visits often evolved into mini focus groups or semi-structured interviews embedded within working environments, enabling observation of how costume workshops spatially integrated new technologies into existing infrastructure, routines, and collaborative practices. The embodied and material dimensions of technology adoption—how practitioners arranged workstations, organised tool access, or negotiated shared equipment—became central to understanding barriers and enablers that textual online data could not capture. These sessions were video- and audio-recorded, with explicit consent obtained, following the same protocols and documentation established for interviews. Field notes captured spatial arrangements, tool configurations, and collaborative interactions observed during visits. Photographs documented workshop layouts, technology use, and integration in production outcomes.

The in-person ethnographic data were processed following the same security protocols as interview data, with recordings saved in .mp4 (video) and .mp3 or .wav (audio) formats, photographs in .jpg format, and field notes digitised as .doc files, all stored on secure Aalto IT systems with network-based backup.

5.3.3. Workshops

Workshop data collection involved video and audio recording of three workshops, each lasting approximately three hours, with 10-20 participants per workshop. Three workshops were carried out. Two in Helsinki, Finland (June and August 2025) and one in Athens, Greece (October 2025). The workshop sessions followed a relatively consistent format and were informed by co-design principles (Zamenopoulos and Alexiou 2018; Kerr et al. 2023). Firstly, the research goals and

workshop objectives were outlined. Next, the tools under investigation were introduced, and their possibilities for costume use were canvassed. This included showing the software in use and providing samples of outcomes. This was followed by a group discussion in which participants shared their thoughts and initial impressions of value, which usually took the first hour of the workshop. The next hour involved providing case study examples from early adopters via posters for practitioners to discuss and annotate in small groups, to generate further reflections and encourage them to relate use to their own context and concerns. This usually included a short tea and coffee break. The balance of the workshop involved small-group activities in which participants were asked to address specific topics related to resource development. This included identifying trusted sources of information, preferred methods of learning, stakeholder mapping activities, prioritising areas of concern and interest, and small- and whole-group discussions exploring the tools and information needed to drive technology adoption.

Audio and video recordings documented workshop conversations, whilst researcher notes and photographs captured written comments, diagrams, sketches, and other materials created during interactive activities. Workshop data was processed and analysed in an identifiable form where explicit consent had been obtained, enabling analysis of correlations between professional experiences and opinions. Video recordings were saved in .mp4 format, audio recordings in .mp3 or .wav format, and stored on secure Aalto IT systems with network-based backup. Transcripts were produced following the same protocols as interview data, with any incidentally revealed special categories of personal data deleted during transcription. All transcripts were saved as .doc files. Photographs of workshop materials were saved as .jpg files, and any handwritten notes or participant comments were manually transcribed into a summary document. Following each workshop, participants were sent follow-up communications thanking them for their time and asking them to complete a survey to offer further reflections or ideas. These comments were added to the workshop analysis materials as a separate word document.

5.3.4. Data Storage and Security

All digital data collected across the three methods was processed and preserved in secure Aalto University IT systems approved for the storage of personal data. Access to computers and IT systems was protected by username and strong personal passwords, with technical restrictions ensuring only researchers participating in the study and persons necessary for implementation had access. A structured folder system and file-naming convention following Aalto IT guidance were implemented. Contact details and consent forms were kept separate from research data throughout the project. Any manual materials (paper consent forms, field notes, workshop materials) were immediately digitised by scanning, saved in accordance with the IT systems data plan, and then stored in locked, monitored cabinets at the researcher's Aalto office before being securely destroyed in accordance with Aalto procedures at project conclusion. For more information about the data management for the project, refer to the project's publicly available data management plan (Taylor 2025c)

5.4. Judgment and Saturation in Data Analysis

Following Guest et al.'s (2006) foundational work demonstrating that saturation in homogeneous populations can be achieved with as few as 12 interviews, the research initially called for 12-20 participants to provide sufficient depth for theory-informed thematic analysis. This wider bracket was determined by the fact there were two technologies under investigation

and multiple adopter categories, which meant the population was likely to be more diverse (Aguinis and Solarino 2019). Through monitoring thematic emergence during concurrent data collection and analysis, the researcher began to recognise that existing themes were becoming informationally redundant at about 20 interviews. However, recruitment continued due to the opportunity to increase geographic and practice diversity for industry dissemination. What was interesting about this project was that the idiosyncratic nature of costume practice meant that, while many of the overarching themes were consistent, the individual creative practices collected remained diverse and unique. This meant that, although theoretically, additional interviews were not generative, for the purposes of industry development further remained instructive and valuable. The final sample of 33 provided robust evidence across adoption categories and enriched the industry-facing outputs.

6. Data Analysis

Data analysis employed a theory-informed thematic coding approach conducted using Atlas.ti qualitative data analysis software. The analytical framework combined two complementary socio-technological theories: domestication theory (Silverstone & Haddon, 1996; Harwood, 2011) and diffusion of innovation theory (Rogers, 2003; Gustafsson et al., 2025). These theoretical lenses structured the research design, informed data collection instruments, and provided analytical scaffolding for coding and interpretation. The analysis process followed established qualitative research protocols, progressing from descriptive first-order codes grounded in participant language to interpretive higher-order codes aligned with theoretical constructs.

6.1. First-Order Analysis

Between April 1 and October 31, all interview transcripts, ethnographic notes and workshop discussion transcripts were imported into Atlas.ti. Initial coding employed multiple strategies to capture the richness and complexity of participant experiences whilst maintaining analytical rigour. Initial structural coding established broad categories corresponding to the interview protocol and research objectives, creating organisational bins for subsequent detailed analysis. These structural codes included technology type (3D printing, digital patternmaking), data source (interview, site visit, workshop) and interview protocol divisions. This was then extended by drawing on the project's theoretical frameworks to begin structuring the data set.

6.2. Higher-Order Codes and Theoretical Analysis

Following initial descriptive coding, focused coding consolidated first-order codes into more conceptual categories aligned with the theoretical frameworks. This iterative process involved constant comparison between codes, identification of patterns across cases, and progressive abstraction towards theoretical constructs.

6.2.1. The domestication theory framework

The domestication theory framework (Silverstone & Haddon, 1996; Harwood, 2011) provided four higher-order coding categories that structured analysis of how practitioners integrated new technologies into their professional lives:

- **Appropriation codes** captured participants' first encounters with technologies, their imagined uses, initial learning experiences, and adoption decisions. This phase encompassed the symbolic and practical work of making technologies meaningful before or during acquisition, including exposure pathways (educational programmes, peer recommendation, professional development), motivation triggers (crisis-driven versus curiosity-driven adoption), and initial attitude formation.
- **Objectification codes** documented the spatial and configurational integration of technologies into physical and digital workspaces. Analysis examined how practitioners configured software programmes, arranged hardware within workshop layouts, negotiated access to shared equipment, and created the material conditions necessary for technology use. This dimension proved particularly revealing of constraints in workshop infrastructure and requirements for collaborative practice.
- **Incorporation codes** analysed how technologies became embedded within temporal routines and production workflows. This included examining whether technologies complemented or replaced existing practices, how practitioners developed habits of use, and how tool deployment became normalised within production schedules. The temporal dimension illuminated tensions between production deadlines and learning curves and revealed strategies for progressive skill development.
- **Conversion codes** explored how practitioners inscribed technologies with personal and professional meanings, and how technology use became part of identity work and professional narratives. The analysis examined how practitioners positioned themselves in relation to craft traditions, how they communicated their use of technology to colleagues and employers, and how adoption reshaped professional self-understanding.

6.2.2. Diffusion Of Innovation Framework

Theoretical coding using Rogers' (2003) diffusion of innovation framework provided a complementary analytical structure organised around perceived attributes of innovations. This framework generated higher-order codes examining:

Barriers to Adoption

- Cost barriers (training time, lost production time, money, individual financial burden)
- Resource constraints (space, equipment, software subscriptions)
- Effectiveness uncertainties (difficulties measuring benefits, uncertain return on investment, limited understanding of possibilities)
- Simplicity challenges (complexity, lack of competence, extensive training requirements, ongoing learning as software changes)
- Compatibility tensions (perceived contrast to costume craft practices and values, resistance among colleagues and management, conservatism toward change)
- Observability limitations (invisible in final performance, requires exposure in workrooms, insecurity about future, awaiting others' proof-of-concept)
- Trialability obstacles (uncertainty about when and how to test)
- Sustainability concerns (environmental costs)

The prevalent and repeating concerns were counterbalanced with codes that identified facilitating factors, with the perceived

Enablers to Adoption:

- Cost enablers (grants and funding, perceived time and money savings)
- Effectiveness drivers (constant time pressures, prizing efficiency)
- Compatibility supports (constant learning normalised within profession)
- Observability facilitators (willingness to share knowledge and teach, desire to move beyond guild models)
- Trialability opportunities (changing collaborators and projects supporting experimentation)
- Sustainability motivations (perceived environmental savings)

6.2.3. Promises Versus Perils of Adoption

Elaborative coding examined the promises versus perils of adoption, a dialectical framework that drew on related and recent work about digital manufacturing technologies in the adjacent field of fashion (Gustafsson et al. 2025).

Promises included sustainability through reduced sampling, efficiency and optimisation, upskilling and reskilling opportunities, alternative income streams (training, digital sales), enhanced communication, high-fidelity prototyping, and open source sharing cultures.

Perils encompass sustainable practices requiring intentional implementation, efficiency used to cut labour costs and employment opportunities, talent pipeline disruptions, outsourcing to cheaper labour pools, intellectual property theft, high-fidelity prototyping that prevents material discoveries, and knowledge democratisation that potentially devalues professional expertise.

6.3. Codebook Development and Data Validation

The coding scheme was developed iteratively through multiple passes through the data. Initial codes were generated from a subset of transcripts, refined, and then systematically applied across the whole dataset. Code definitions were documented, including inclusion/exclusion criteria and exemplar quotes, to ensure consistency.

The final codebook integrated structural organisation and higher-order theoretical codes (domestication phases, diffusion attributes, promises/perils dialectic). This multi-layered coding structure enabled both fine-grained analysis of participant experiences and systematic examination of patterns aligned with theoretical constructs. The codebook served as both an analytical framework during the research process and a transparency mechanism for documenting analytical decisions. See Appendix 9 for the final codebook.

When participant accounts conflicted (e.g., some viewing digital tools as time-saving, others as time-intensive), these contradictions were explored through subsequent interviews and contextualised within participants' different employment situations, values, and prior technical experience rather than ignored or resolved toward consensus.

7. Unexpected Opportunities, Challenges, and Adaptive Measures

The TICP project encountered significant challenges in digital ethnography data collection that necessitated methodological adaptation. Initial plans involved longitudinal content analysis of large, established online costume networks, particularly Facebook groups with substantial membership. However, access proved tricky: group administrators were often unresponsive to consent requests, and obtaining explicit informed consent from multiple group members for

data collection and publication was neither feasible nor ethically justifiable. Further, the use of even publicly available data is deemed ethically problematic (Buck and Ralston 2021; Flick et al. 2018; The National Committee for Research Ethics in the Social Sciences and the Humanities 2019). Rather than proceeding with ambiguous ethical standing, the researcher discontinued digital ethnography in these spaces, recognising that research integrity required transparency and genuine consent, rather than data volume. This challenge, whilst initially appearing as a project constraint, generated an unexpected opportunity. The shift toward in-person workshop visits and site-based data collection revealed dimensions of technological adoption invisible in online discourse alone. These visits often evolved into mini focus groups or semi-structured interviews embedded within working environments, enabling observation of how costume workshops spatially integrated new technologies into existing infrastructure, routines, and collaborative practices. The embodied and material dimensions of technology adoption, how practitioners arranged workstations, organised tool access, or negotiated shared equipment, became central to understanding barriers and enablers that textual online data could not capture. This methodological pivot enriched the research by foregrounding the socio-material context essential to sociotechnical theory, ultimately yielding more nuanced findings about technology adoption than the initially planned approach would have.

A second significant development emerged from an unexpected disciplinary opening. During the fellowship, the researcher identified and responded to a conference call for papers focused on costume narratives. This submission led to the development of narrative analysis as an analytical framework, one not initially planned in the TICP methodology, applied to interview data to examine how practitioners constructed and negotiated meaning in relation to technological change. This framework proved remarkably generative, producing one of the project's key findings regarding how practitioners narrate their professional identities in relation to technological adoption. Notably, narrative analysis aligned coherently with the broader Science and Technology Studies (STS) theories underpinning TICP (domestication and diffusion theories), enriching rather than displacing the original theoretical architecture. The unplanned focus on narrative demonstrates how engagement with disciplinary conversations and responsiveness to emerging analytical possibilities can strengthen findings.

A final unexpected challenge concerned participant oversubscription: interest in the project substantially exceeded anticipated engagement, creating the unusual situation where some potential participants could not be accommodated, and more than double the expected number of interviews were conducted, which produced a surfeit of data to be processed and analysed. While a stressor to project resources, rather than representing a deficit, this surplus indicated substantial practitioner investment in the research topic and high professional interest in technology adoption conversations. The researcher managed this by purposefully selecting participants to ensure diversity across adoption positions, geographic locations, and employment contexts, transforming oversubscription into an opportunity to strengthen participant diversity and representativeness.

8. Limitations

This research acknowledges several methodological limitations that shaped data collection, analysis, and the transferability of findings. The single-researcher coding structure, whilst enabling deep familiarity with the dataset and consistency in code application, potentially

limited interpretive breadth. Although regular supervisory and research group meetings provided external perspective and validation checkpoints for analytical decisions, the absence of formal inter-rater reliability testing means that alternative interpretations of the data remained unexplored. This limitation is characteristic of postdoctoral research conducted within resource constraints, but future studies might benefit from collaborative coding teams to strengthen analytical rigour and reveal interpretive possibilities that a single researcher's perspective may obscure.

The focus on two specific Industry 4.0 technologies—digital patternmaking software and 3D printing—enabled depth of investigation but limits claims about technology adoption more broadly. These technologies share certain characteristics (digital interfaces, requirement for specialised hardware, disruption to established craft workflows) that may not extend to other I4.0 tools relevant to costume practice, such as digital textile printing, laser cutting or computer-aided embroidery. Each technology presents distinct barriers, learning curves, and compatibility tensions with existing practice. Findings regarding domestication processes and adoption barriers for the two case study technologies may not transfer directly to technologies with different operational requirements or symbolic meanings within costume practice.

Geographic concentration presented a third limitation. Whilst the study recruited internationally, participants were predominantly located in English-speaking countries (Australia, United Kingdom, United States, Canada) and Europe, with limited representation from Asia (2), Africa (0) or South America (1). Participants were also limited to those who spoke English. This geographic and linguistic concentration reflects the researcher's professional networks and language capacities, but may limit the generalisability of findings to contexts with different theatrical traditions, economic structures, or relationships to digital technology. Workshop data collection was similarly concentrated, with all three workshops held in Europe (Finland and Greece). Different cultural contexts for costume practice, varying infrastructure for digital manufacturing, and distinct relationships between craft traditions and technological innovation in non-Western contexts may produce adoption patterns not captured in this study.

Workshop participant self-selection introduced potential sampling bias. Participants who elected to attend co-design workshops on technology adoption were likely more interested in, curious about, or already engaged with these technologies than the broader costume professional population. This self-selection effect may have skewed workshop discussions towards more positive attitudes about technological possibilities and away from perspectives of practitioners who are sceptical, resistant, or unable to engage with digital tools. Similarly, interview participants, particularly early adopters, were purposively selected for their existing engagement with the technologies, creating a sample weighted towards those with successful adoption experiences. Whilst the inclusion of early majority adopters who were newer to the technologies partially addressed this limitation, as did visits to workshops which included talking to those not interested or actively against digital costume practices, practitioners who actively rejected these technologies or lacked access to them remain underrepresented in the dataset.

In this vein, the methodological shift from planned digital ethnography to site-based visits, whilst enriching the research by foregrounding socio-material dimensions of technology adoption, meant that the study captured fewer perspectives from practitioners who discuss technology adoption online but have not yet implemented these tools in their practice. The original digital ethnography design would have enabled observation of discourse from non-users and sceptics whose voices may be less prominent in interview and workshop data. This

pivot, though ethically necessary, potentially reduced access to practitioner ambivalence and resistance that might be more freely expressed in online professional communities than in face-to-face research encounters.

Finally, the temporal constraints of a 13-month postdoctoral fellowship limited the longitudinal scope of the research. Technology adoption is a process that unfolds over months and years, involving iterative cycles of learning, experimentation, abandonment, and re-engagement. This study captured practitioners' adoption experiences at a single point in time through retrospective accounts and observations of current practice but could not track how individual practitioners' relationships with these technologies evolved across production cycles or career stages. Longitudinal research following practitioners over several years as they navigate technology adoption could provide richer insight into the timeframes involved in domestication processes and the factors that sustain or undermine technological adoption over time.

Despite these limitations, the study's theoretical framework, multi-method design, and diverse participant sample provide robust evidence regarding technology adoption in professional costume practice. The findings offer valuable insights for practitioners, educators, and industry stakeholders, whilst acknowledging that further research in different geographic contexts, with different technologies, and employing longitudinal designs would strengthen and extend this work.

9. Conclusions

This methodology documentation report demonstrates how TICP's cross-disciplinary approach applies theories from science and technology studies (STS) to costume research, offering valuable theoretical and methodological insights for the field. The research design combines domestication theory and diffusion of innovation theory to examine how practitioners integrate digital patternmaking and 3D printing into their professional practices, recognising that users actively shape technological adoption rather than passively accepting innovations. Through practitioner interviews, site-based ethnography, and co-design workshops, the methodology captures both individual experiences and collective professional discourse, providing comprehensive insight into technology adoption barriers and enablers.

The project's methodological innovation comes from bringing STS theoretical rigour to practical questions about professional development and technological change in costume practice. This approach proved sufficiently novel to warrant dissemination through direct engagement with research communities and the establishment of an international peer feedback circle of researchers applying STS theories to theatre production. For future research, this methodology offers transferable value beyond costume practice. The technology adoption model developed through this framework can potentially address digitalisation challenges in other craft-based theatre areas, whilst the demonstrated viability of applying STS theories to live performance opens new avenues for examining sociotechnical change across creative industries.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Interview Participation Info Sheet

Appendix 2: Interview Privacy Notice

Appendix 3: Interview Consent Form

Appendix 4: Interview Protocol

Appendix 5: Co-design Workshop Participation Info Sheet

Appendix 6: Co-design Workshop Privacy Notice

Appendix 7: Co-design Workshop Consent Form

Appendix 8: Co-design Workshop Flyer

Appendix 9: Analysis Codebook

Aalto University

Participant Information for Research Project

Technological Innovations in Costume Practice

Ethics Approval Number D/1785/03.04/2025

– Interviews –

Research stakeholders

<i>Party</i>	<i>Role</i>
Madeline Taylor	Marie Curie Postdoctoral Research Fellow / Researcher
Sofia Pantouvaki	Professor / Supervisor
Aalto University	Ethics approval and guidance
European Union via Horizon Europe	Funding body

Purpose - Why is the study being conducted?

This research study examines live performance costume professionals' experiences with and responses to new design and manufacturing technologies, specifically virtual patternmaking software and 3D printing. It investigates the value of these tools for costume practice, how people are implementing them in their workflow, and what the barriers and facilitators are for their adoption.

You are invited to participate in this research project because you have expertise and valuable perspective in this area. The research from this project may help to contribute to advice and tools for individual practitioners, companies, governments and funding bodies on processes and practices involved in a transition to new costume design and manufacturing technologies.

What does participation involve?

Participation activity and duration: Participation involves an interview, in which you will be invited to talk about your experiences with the nominated technologies. The interview will be done online over Zoom or similar platform. It is expected the interview will take 1-1.5 hours maximum. Interview questions will cover the 'story' of your experiences with the technology so far, your work history and professional practices, and how you interact with others in the costume team with these technologies. If relevant, in the second half of the interview you will be invited to share a current or recent project using the technology via screen sharing to talk about the specifics of your practice. The interviews will be video and audio recorded for later review and transcription. During the screen sharing, the interviewer might ask permission to take screen shots of your work. You can decline this if you wish.

Participation is Voluntary: This research is entirely voluntary. Your decision to participate or not participate will in no way impact your current or future relationship with Aalto University. Before you consent to the research, you will have the opportunity to ask any questions. If you do agree to participate, you can later withdraw from the research project without comment, penalty or any obligation to disclose any specific reasons for discontinuing by emailing the researcher.

What are the possible benefits for me if I take part?

Personal benefits of being part of the research include an opportunity to reflect on your own practice and career, have your skills and knowledge acknowledged publicly (if you wish) and be part of an

APPENDIX 1

international conversation about the costuming industry. The findings from this research will be used to generate publications, advice and tools for individual practitioners and companies on processes and practices involved in a transition to new costume design and manufacturing technologies, which will be shared with you if you wish.

Compensation: There is no compensation offered for participating.

What are the possible risks or disadvantages to me for participating? How will these be minimised or treated?

Risks from participating include the economic inconvenience of the time required to participate, and the mental/emotional discomfort of being interviewed and sharing details about your work history and relationships, which you might find uncomfortable. The economic inconvenience will be reduced by scheduling the interview at a time that suits you. The mental/emotional discomfort will be minimised with the provision of this information, discussion beforehand of the research and any questions you have about it, and your ability to request we skip or move on from any question.

How do I give my consent to participate?

We ask you to sign a written consent form (attached) to confirm your consent to participate, how you want to be credited and how researchers can use any images if collected.

What if I have questions or need more information about the research project?

Please contact:

Madeline Taylor (Redacted)

What if I have a research related injury, or concern/complaint about the conduct of the research?

Aalto University is committed to following the national guidelines for research ethics and integrity. If you wish to discuss the study with someone not directly involved, particularly in relation to matters concerning information or complaints about the conduct of the study or your rights as a participant, you can contact the Aalto Research Ethics Committee via this website:

<https://www.aalto.fi/en/services/research-ethics-review-research-ethics-committee>, or submit a complaint via the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK: <https://tenk.fi>

Thank you for helping with this research project. Please keep this sheet for your information.

Privacy Notice for Research Project

Aalto University

Technical Innovation in Costume Practice

Ethics Approval Number D/1785/03.04/2025

– Interviews –

This privacy notice describes how your personal data will be used in the research study as a participating individual. You have also been provided with document called “Participant Information Sheet”, which explains in more detail how the study is carried out.

Research stakeholders

<i>Party</i>	<i>Role</i>
Madeline Taylor	Marie Curie Postdoctoral Research Fellow / Researcher
Sofia Pantouvaki	Professor / Supervisor
Aalto University	Ethics approval and guidance
European Union via Horizon Europe	Funding body

1. What is being studied in this research study and the purpose of processing personal data

This research study examines live performance costume professionals’ experiences with and responses to new design and manufacturing technologies, specifically virtual patternmaking software and 3D printing. It investigates the value of these tools for costume practice, how people are implementing them in their workflow, and what the barriers and facilitators are for their adoption.

This research is funded by the European Union via a Marie Skłodowska Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship.

2. What personal data is processed in the research study?

Personal data collected by the interview will include:

- Your name
- Contact details (email address or phone number) for organising interviews and other research communication (e.g. sharing findings afterward)
- Interview responses, which will be transcribed and may include
 - Professional title and work experience in the field in years
 - Details of work experience (e.g. productions worked on, type of work done)
 - Location data (city or country where work has been carried out)
 - Current and past employer name/s or area (e.g. dance, theatre)
- Video recordings showing your face and hands/gestures (e.g. showing how you use a tool)
- With additional permission, images of creative works, in the form of screen shots
- PDF consent form including name and signature

Special categories of personal data (sensitive personal data)

Data belonging to special categories of personal data or other specially protected personal data **will not be processed** in the research study.

Appendix 2: Interview Privacy Notice

Data belonging to special categories of personal data or other specially protected personal data will not explicitly be collected in the research. However, it is possible that information classified as special categories of personal data (such as political opinions or belonging to Trade Unions) may come up as a result of discussion during interviews. When processing data collected from the study, data belonging to special categories of personal data will be deleted from the transcript.

Personal data is collected from the following sources: Directly from you, the study participant, in the form of an interview.

The research methods for collecting this data are described to you more in detail in the “Participant Information Sheet” document.

3. Processing of necessary personal data and removal of the direct identifiers from the data

The research study only processes personal data that is necessary for the purpose and execution of the study.

Interview data will be processed and analysed in an identifiable form, as the data analysis will involve analysis of video recordings in which participants are visible and recognisable. To minimise the collection of personal data:

- Contact details and consent forms will be kept separate from research data and will not be made public
- If the research participant reveals sensitive personal data, this will be deleted during transcription
- Personal data such as workplace or location will not be published without consent
- Recordings of the interviews will not be published/made public
- Screenshots of past or current work will not be published/made public without your explicit written consent.
- The identity of the individual research participant will not be disclosed /published without explicit written consent. Note that participants can request to be pseudonymous for publication. However, as recognising the professional expertise of costumers is one motivation for the research, this pseudonymous position will not be by default.

4. Legal Basis for the processing of personal data

The processing of personal data is based on scientific research, a task in the public interest

5. Sharing personal data

Research data containing your personal data is shared with the following parties:

Independent controllers: The Researcher, Madeline Taylor will be an Independent Controller following the end of the postdoctoral project.

Further, research data which consists of your personal data, may be transferred to a third party, such as scientific publication, for peer-review process or for other purpose, which is mandatory for scientific publishing or validation of the research results. Research data containing personal data is retained for research data to be used for further scientific research in the same scientific discipline or in other

Appendix 2: Interview Privacy Notice

disciplines that support this research study. As part of this research data may also be transferred to other universities or research organisations as part of further research projects.

Processors: No external processors (e.g. transcription services or analysts) will be used for this data.

6. International data transfers

Research data containing personal data will be transferred to non-EU / EEA countries. Once the Researcher's (Madeline Taylor) contract with Aalto University finishes in December 2025, she and a copy of the data will transfer to Australia. To ensure that the transfer complies with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation this transfer copy is subject an Agreement between the controllers using EU / EEA model contract clauses.

Further as part of the scientific publishing process, it might be necessary to transfer the data outside EU/EEA for publishers or peer reviewers for verification of research results, as such parties may be located outside EU/EEA area. However, it is exceptional that scientific publication process would require transferring data regarded as personal data.

7. Storage and protection of personal data

Protection of manual material: Any manual material collected (e.g. paper consent forms or observation notes) will be immediately digitised using Aalto hardware/printers (scanned, emailed and saved as per the below IT systems data plan) then securely destroyed (following Aalto procedures).

Information processed in IT systems: Your personal data is processed and preserved in secure IT systems, which are approved by Aalto University and suitable for personal data. Access to all computers and IT systems are protected by username and strong personal password. Access to IT systems containing personal data is technically restricted in a manner, that only researchers participating in the study and persons necessary for the implementation of the study have access to your personal data.

8. Retention and deletion of personal data

Deletion during and after the study: Research data containing personal data will be retained further scientific research in the same scientific discipline or in other disciplines that support this research study. Research data containing personal data is deleted after five (5) years since the last publication where this research data has been used and exploited and at the latest ten (10) years after the end of the postdoctoral project.

9. Rights of the research participant

According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), a data subject has the right to:

- receive information on the processing of their personal data
- right to access the personal data collected and processed
- right to rectification of inaccurate personal data
- request that the processing of personal data be restricted
- object the processing of personal data
- right to erasure of personal data if the conditions of Article 17(1) of the Data Protection Regulation are met and processing is no longer necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest or for scientific research or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1)

Appendix 2: Interview Privacy Notice

If the research purpose does not require, or no longer requires the identification of the data subject, the controller shall not be obliged to obtain further information so that the data or the data subject may be identified only for purposes to enable the data subject to exercise his/her rights. If the controller is unable to link the data to a particular data subject, the data subject does not have the right to access or correct the personal data, object the processing, or delete the personal data. However, if the data subject provides additional information that allows their identification from the research data, the rights will not be restricted.

10. Contact details of the controller

The controller for personal data processing is Aalto University Foundation sr., operating as Aalto University. After the 14.12.2025 Madeline Taylor is an additional independent controller.

Person in charge of the research study: Questions regarding the conduct of the research study may be addressed to the person in charge of the study: Madeline Taylor at XXX until 14 Dec 2025, thereafter at XXXX

Data Protection Officer: If the research participant has questions or requests related to data protection or the processing of personal data, the research participant should contact the Data Protection Officer of Aalto University at XXXXX

In this data request service, you can request the exercise of your rights under GDPR from Aalto University as the controller <https://datarequest.aalto.fi/en-US/>.

If a participant of the research study feels that his or her personal data has been processed in violation of data protection legislation, the participant has the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority, the Data Protection Ombudsman's office (read more: <http://www.tietosuoja.fi>).

Thank you for helping with this research project. Please keep this sheet for your information.

Appendix 3: Interview Consent Form

Aalto University

Technical Innovation in Costume Practice

Ethics Approval Number D/1785/03.04/2025

– Interview Consent Form –

I acknowledge I have read and understood the Participant Information sheet and Privacy Notice, had the opportunity to have my questions answered, and wish to participate in the research via a recorded interview.

I understand that participation is voluntary, and I can withdraw at any point, but up until my withdrawal, all information gathered can be used as described in the Privacy Notice. I understand that if I wish to withdraw, I just need to email Madeline.

Name of research participant: _____

Signature (Note: a digital or typed signature is fine): _____

Date: _____

Publication of information I provide (PLEASE SELECT/CIRCLE ONE)		
I retain copyright, but I agree that my words may be quoted in research publications.	Yes	No
In any acknowledgement lists, or when quoting or referring to my words or work in any research publications I prefer to be: (Note that as a way to acknowledge costumer’s expertise and your contributions, we are keen to credit you, but this is optional)	Credited	Pseudonymous
I retain copyright of my creative work, but I agree that the visuals of my work I share in the interview might be included in research publications (appropriately credited).	Yes	No
My past experience (e.g. role, productions worked on), production company name or general location of work (e.g. city or country) can be included in publications or research acknowledgements	Yes	No
Please send me a copy of any publications arising from the research	Yes	No

What if I have questions or need more information about the research project?

Please contact: Madeline Taylor XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX

Appendix 4: Interview Protocol

TICP Interview protocol

The interview participation invitation outlined this as the topic of interest: Interview questions will cover the 'story' of your experiences with the technology so far, your work history and professional practices, and how you interact with others in the costume team using these technologies. If relevant, in the second half of the interview, you will be invited to share a current or recent project using the technology via screen sharing to talk about the specifics of your practice.

At start of the interview:

Introduce self and project. Confirm recording approval and discuss expectations around shared screen/work shown.

Can you tell me the story of your career when you started using XXX tech?

- Probe examples:
 - How and why you got started? Your first encounters with a technology, what you thought of it prior to adoption and how that matched reality?
 - What issues occurred prior or during adoption?
 - Did you trial it in some way?
 - Where or who did you learn from? Did you do any digital tech training as part of your career prep?
 - When /why did you decide to go all in? (What does all in mean to you)?
 - How long did you take to feel 'expert'? (time in years, productions, garments)
 - Are you still using / will keep using? How and why?
 - How do you see this adoption influencing your career?

Where do you do this work / Can you tell me about the space you work in?

- Physically where do you work? In the company spaces or remote? (if remote home or elsewhere?) Own/Same computer / different?
- Digitally Where do you do this work? Shared drives? Desktop? What 'space' do you use on the computer - how do you share or not the files and patterns you create?
- How are you sharing / working together? Eg online, offline?

What did using this tech replace in previous process? How is it part of your routine / practice?

- Processes:
 - What did this make easier?
 - What did it make more difficult?

Appendix 4: Interview Protocol

- Creativity:
 - What did this make easier?
 - What did it make more difficult?
- Collaboration:
 - What did this make easier?
 - What did it make more difficult?

Can you share a current or recent project using the technology via screen sharing to talk about the specifics of your practice?

- Talk me through your workflow - tools/software and stages?

Are you sharing your work with this tool/ process with others?

- Can you see it influencing others' activities?
- Sharing outcomes / transparency of practice – how / where?
- Who are you now working with / teaching (if relevant)?

What do you think are the general attitudes to digital technologies/tools for costume work among your work colleagues / your local costume network?

What do you see as the potential for the future with XXX technology?

Thank for time and close interview

Aalto University

Participant Information for Research Project

Technical Innovation in Costume Practice

Ethics Approval Number D/1784/03.04/2025

– Co-design workshop –

Research stakeholders

<u>Party</u>	<u>Role</u>
Madeline Taylor	Marie Curie Postdoctoral Research Fellow / Researcher
Sofia Pantouvaki	Professor / Supervisor
Aalto University	Ethics approval and guidance
European Union via Horizon Europe	Funding body

Purpose - Why is the study being conducted?

This research examines how live performance costume professionals adopt new manufacturing technologies, specifically virtual patternmaking software and 3D printing. Through interviews and observations with practitioners, we have gathered insights on these technologies' value, implementation methods, and factors that help or hinder adoption.

We now invite you to participate in a workshop where we will transform these research findings into practical tools and guidance for the costume industry. Your expertise as a costume professional is valuable in helping create resources that will support practitioners and companies who wish to integrate these technologies into their work.

What does participation involve?

Participation activity and duration: Participation involves attending a 3-hour co-design workshop (excluding breaks) where you will:

1. Learn about virtual patternmaking and 3D printing technologies through presentations and demonstrations
2. Hear key findings from our research project
3. Participate in small group activities including mapping, brainstorming, and providing critical feedback to help develop practical tools for the costume industry

The workshop will be documented in several ways:

- Video recording of discussions for later review and transcription
- Photography or scanning of visual materials you create (sketches, diagrams, notes)
- Researcher notes on comments and ideas shared during the session

Participation is Voluntary: This research is entirely voluntary. Your decision to participate will not affect your relationship with Aalto University, either now or in the future.

Before consenting, you are welcome to ask any questions about the research. If you agree to participate and later change your mind, you can withdraw by simply emailing the researcher. No explanation is required, and there are no penalties for withdrawing.

What are the possible benefits for me if I take part?

The personal benefits of being part of the research include the opportunity to learn more about these technologies, reflect on your own practice and career, and participate in an international conversation about the costuming industry. Participating may also help you to build your professional networks.

Appendix 5: Co-design workshop Participation Info sheet

The findings from this research will be used to generate publications, advice and tools for individual practitioners and companies on processes and practices involved in a transition to new costume design and manufacturing technologies, which will be shared with the participants if you wish.

Compensation: The workshop will include catering (coffee/tea/cake and lunch). There is no payment for participating.

What are the possible risks or disadvantages to me for participating?

How will these be minimised or treated?

Risks from participating include the economic inconvenience of the time required to participate, and the emotional discomfort of sharing details about your work practices, history and professional relationships, which you might find uncomfortable. The economic inconvenience will be reduced by scheduling the workshop with lots of notice as to time and date, and it being entirely voluntary. The emotional discomfort will be mitigated by not requiring people to contribute to any particular task or question, activities focused on small groups, and your ability to withdraw at any time without penalty. The workshop activities do not pose any physical risk beyond normal day-to-day activity. In the unlikely event of an emergency, venue security and first aid will be available to help.

Insurance coverage: You are covered by an insurance policy, purchased by Aalto University, to cover any accidents and damages occurring during the workshop.

How do I give my consent to participate?

We ask you to sign a written consent form (supplied) to confirm your consent to participate, how you want to be credited and how researchers can use any images if collected.

What if I have questions or need more information about the research project?

Please contact:

Madeline Taylor

madeline.taylor@aalto.fi

+358503095052

What if I have a research related injury, or concern/complaint about the conduct of the research?

Aalto University is committed to following the national guidelines for research ethics and integrity. If you wish to discuss the study with someone not directly involved, particularly in relation to matters concerning information or complaints about the conduct of the study or your rights as a participant, you can contact the Aalto Research Ethics Committee via this website:

<https://www.aalto.fi/en/services/research-ethics-review-research-ethics-committee>, or submit a complaint via the Finnish National Board on Research Integrity TENK: <https://tenk.fi>

Thank you for helping with this research project. Please keep this sheet for your information.

Privacy Notice for Research Project

Aalto University

Technical Innovation in Costume Practice

Ethics Approval Number D/1784/03.04/2025

– Co-design workshop participants –

This privacy notice describes how your personal data will be used in the research study as a participating individual. You have also been provided with document called “Participant Information Sheet”, which explains in more detail how the study is carried out.

Research stakeholders

<i>Party</i>	<i>Role</i>
Madeline Taylor	Marie Curie Postdoctoral Research Fellow / Researcher
Sofia Pantouvaki	Professor / Supervisor
Aalto University	Ethics approval and guidance
European Union via Horizon Europe	Funding body

1. What is being studied in this research study and the purpose of processing personal data

This research study examines live performance costume professionals’ experiences with and responses to new design and manufacturing technologies, specifically virtual patternmaking software and 3D printing. It investigates the value of these tools for costume practice, how people are implementing them in their workflow, and what the barriers and facilitators are for their adoption.

This research is funded by the European Union via a Marie Skłodowska Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship.

2. What personal data is processed in the research study?

Personal data collected during the co-design workshops will include:

- Name and contact details (email address or phone number) for organising participation and other research communication (e.g. sharing findings afterward)
- Video / audio recordings of some workshop conversations showing participants faces
- Transcriptions of workshop conversation, which may include
 - Opinions of technologies and professional experiences
 - Professional title and work experience in the field in years
 - Details of work experience (e.g. productions worked on, type of work done)
 - Location data (city, state or country where work has been carried out)
 - Current and past employer name/s or area (e.g. dance, theatre)
- Written comments, in the form of opinions and notes on workshop activities and tasks
- Images of creative works, in the form of doodles, diagrams or sketches made during the workshop
- Findings or notes made by the researcher about their comments and contributions to the conversation
- Consent form including name and signature

Special categories of personal data (sensitive personal data)

Data belonging to special categories of personal data or other specially protected personal data **will not be processed** in the research study.

Appendix 6: Co-Design Workshop Privacy Notice

Personal data is collected from the following sources: Directly from the participant, from the researcher's observations

The research methods for collecting this data are described to you more in detail in the "Participant Information Sheet" document.

3. Processing of necessary personal data and removal of the direct identifiers from the data

The research study only processes personal data that is necessary for the purpose and execution of the study.

Workshop data will be processed and analysed in an identifiable form, as the data analysis will involve analysis of video recordings in which participants are visible and recognisable. To minimise the collection of personal data:

- Contact details and consent forms will be kept separate from research data and will not be made public
- In case the research participant reveals sensitive or special category personal data, such data will be deleted in the transcription phase.
- Personal data such as workplace or location data will not be published without consent
- Recordings of the workshops will not be published/made public
- Images made in the workshop will not be published/made public without explicit written consent.
- The identity of the individual research participant will not be disclosed in a scientific publication or other published research results without explicit written consent. Note that participants can request to be pseudonymous for publication. However, as recognising the professional expertise of costumers is one motivation for the research, this pseudonymous position will not be by default.

4. Legal Basis for the processing of personal data

The processing of personal data is based on scientific research, a task in the public interest

5. Sharing personal data

Research data containing your personal data is shared with the following parties:

Independent controllers: The Researcher, Madeline Taylor will be an Independent Controller following the end of the postdoctoral project.

Further, research data which consists of your personal data, may be transferred to a third party, such as scientific publication, for peer-review process or for other purpose, which is mandatory for scientific publishing or validation of the research results. Research data containing personal data is retained for research data to be used for further scientific research in the same scientific discipline or in other disciplines that support this research study. As part of this research data may also be transferred to other universities or research organisations as part of further research projects.

Processors: No external processors (e.g. transcription services or analysts) will be used for this data.

6. International data transfers

Research data containing personal data will be transferred to non-EU / EEA countries. Once the Researcher's (Madeline Taylor) contract with Aalto University finishes in December 2025, she and a copy of the data will transfer to Australia. To ensure that the transfer complies with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation this transfer copy is subject an Agreement between the controllers using EU / EEA model contract clauses.

Further as part of the scientific publishing process, it might be necessary to transfer the data outside EU/EAA for publishers or peer reviewers for verification of research results, as such parties may be located outside EU/EAA area. However, it is exceptional that scientific publication process would require transferring data regarded as personal data.

7. Storage and protection of personal data

Protection of manual material: Any manual material collected (e.g. paper consent forms, workshop worksheets or observation notes) will be immediately digitised (scanned and saved as per the below IT systems data plan) then securely destroyed (following Aalto procedures).

Information processed in IT systems: Your personal data is processed and preserved in secure IT systems, which are approved by Aalto University and suitable for personal data. Access to all computers and IT systems are protected by username and strong personal password. Access to IT systems containing personal data is technically restricted in a manner, that only researchers participating in the study and persons necessary for the implementation of the study have access to your personal data.

8. Retention and deletion of personal data

Deletion during and after the study: Research data containing personal data will be retained further scientific research in the same scientific discipline or in other disciplines that support this research study. Research data containing personal data is deleted after five (5) years since the last publication where this research data has been used and exploited and at the latest ten (10) years after the end of the postdoctoral project.

9. Rights of the research participant

According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), a data subject has the right to:

- receive information on the processing of their personal data
- right to access the personal data collected and processed
- right to rectification of inaccurate personal data
- request that the processing of personal data be restricted
- object the processing of personal data
- right to erasure of personal data if the conditions of Article 17(1) of the Data Protection Regulation are met and processing is no longer necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest or for scientific research or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1)

If the research purpose does not require, or no longer requires the identification of the data subject, the controller shall not be obliged to obtain further information so that the data or the data subject may be identified only for purposes to able the data subject to exercise his/her rights. If the controller is unable to link the data to a particular data subject, the data subject does not have the right to access or correct the personal data, object the processing, or delete the personal data. However, if the data subject provides additional information that allows their identification from the research data, the rights will not be restricted.

10. Contact details of the controller

The controller for personal data processing is Aalto University Foundation sr., operating as Aalto University. After the 14.12.2025 Madeline Taylor is an additional independent controller.

Person in charge of the research study: Questions regarding the conduct of the research study may be addressed to the person in charge of the study: Madeline Taylor (redacted)

Data Protection Officer: If the research participant has questions or requests related to data protection or the processing of personal data, the research participant should contact the Data Protection Officer of Aalto University (redacted). In this data request service, you can request the exercise of your rights under GDPR from Aalto University as the controller. If a participant of the research study feels that his or her personal data has been processed in violation of data protection legislation, the participant has the right to lodge a complaint with the supervisory authority, the Data Protection Ombudsman's office (read more: <http://www.tietosuoja.fi>).

Thank you for helping with this research project. Please keep this sheet for your information.

Appendix 7: Co-Design Workshop Consent Form

	Consent form for Research Project
	Technical Innovation in Costume Practice Ethics Approval Number D/1784/03.04/2025 – Co-design Workshop Participation –

I have received, read and understood the Participant information and Privacy Notice, had the opportunity to have my questions answered, and wish to participate in the research study.

I have understood that participation is voluntary and I can withdraw from the research study at any point, but up until my withdrawal all information gathered can be used as described in the Privacy Notice. I understand if I wish to withdraw, I just need to email the researcher.

Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

Publication of the information I provide (please select one)		
While I retain copyright of my words and work, I understand and agree that my words may be quoted and any visuals I create in the workshop might be published or referred to in any research publications.	Yes	No
As one of the goals of the study is recognising the skill and expertise of costumers, our preference is to openly acknowledge your contribution by name in any research publications. In any acknowledgements, or when quoting or referring to my work I prefer to be:	Credited	Pseudonymous
May we include your company name/ general location of work (e.g. city or country) in any publications or research acknowledgements?	Yes	No
Please send me a copy of any publications arising from the research	Yes	No
If yes, my email is:		

What if I have questions or need more information about the research project?

Please contact: Madeline Taylor (redacted)

COSTUME PROFESSIONALS OF FINLAND
ARE INVITED TO ATTEND A

Costume Technologies Workshop

FREE

For the last six months, the Technological Innovations in Costume Practice research project has explored costume professionals' experiences with new design and manufacturing technologies, specifically digital patternmaking and 3D printing tools. We are now running workshops to share what we have found and co-develop resources for industry.

Come along and:

- Learn what these technologies offer for costume work
- Hear about the research findings so far, and
- Share your advice and ideas about creating practical resources for the costume industry from the research

Thursday 12 June
OR
Thursday 28 August

Sadly, workshops are only in English
Some sections will be recorded for
research purposes

Aalto University Costume workshop
Otakaari 7, 02150, ESPOO

9-12 (est. 3hrs)
Plus included lunch to follow if
you wish

**TO REGISTER OR FOR MORE
INFORMATION CONTACT:**

madeline.taylor@aalto.fi

Funded by
the European Union

Note that this study has been approved by the Aalto University
Research Ethics Committee (Approval number D/1784/03.04/2025).

Aalto University
School of Arts, Design
and Architecture

TICP Data Analysis Codebook

1. Overview

This codebook documents the analytical framework and coding scheme employed in the TICP research project examining technology adoption in professional costume practice. The analysis combines theory-informed thematic coding with inductive approaches, progressing from descriptive first-order codes to interpretive higher-order theoretical codes. Data analysis was conducted using Atlas.ti qualitative data analysis software.

1.1 Theoretical Framework

The analytical framework integrates two complementary socio-technological theories:

- **Domestication Theory** (Silverstone & Haddon, 1996; Harwood, 2011; Landmark et al., 2024): Examines how users integrate technologies into their professional lives through symbolic and practical work across four non-sequential phases: appropriation, objectification, incorporation, and conversion.
- **Diffusion of Innovation Theory** (Rogers, 2003): Focuses on perceived attributes of innovations that influence adoption decisions: relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability.

2. First-Order Coding Strategies

First-order codes focused on structuring the data into useable and understandable divisions of participant experiences whilst maintaining analytical rigour. Structural Codes establish broad organisational categories corresponding to research design:

- **Technology type:** 3D printing, digital patternmaking
- **Data source:** Interview, site visit, workshop
- **Interview protocol divisions:** narrative, semi-structured questions, project tour

3. Higher-Order Codes: Domestication Theory Framework

Focused coding consolidated first-order codes into conceptual categories aligned with domestication theory's four phases:

Phase and definition	Subcodes
<p>APPROPRIATION First encounters with technologies, Encompasses symbolic and practical work of making technologies meaningful before or during acquisition.</p>	<p>Imagined use Learning Adoption decision Exposure pathways (education, peer recommendation, professional development) Motivation triggers (crisis-driven, curiosity-driven, situational)</p>
<p>OBJECTIFICATION Spatial and configurational integration of technologies into physical and digital workspaces. Reveals workshop infrastructure constraints and collaborative practice requirements.</p>	<p>Software / digital configuration and systems Hardware configuration within workshop Negotiating access to shared equipment Material conditions necessary for technology use</p>

Appendix 9: Analysis Codebook

Phase and definition	Subcodes
<p>INCORPORATION Integration into temporal routines and production workflows. Illuminates tensions between production deadlines and learning curves.</p>	<p>Creating routines of use/ Habit development Complementing or replacing existing practices Tool use becoming normal Strategies for progressive skill development</p>
<p>CONVERSION How practitioners inscribe technologies with personal and professional meanings, and how technology use becomes part of identity work and professional narratives.</p>	<p>Personal values Positioning in relation to craft traditions Sustainability Professional narratives/ Reshaping professional self Communicating tech use to colleagues and employers</p>

Note: These phases are non-sequential and may occur simultaneously or iteratively throughout the adoption process.

4. Higher-Order Codes: Diffusion of Innovation Framework

Theoretical coding using Rogers' (2003) diffusion of innovation framework examined perceived attributes of innovations influencing adoption:

4.1 Barriers to Adoption

Barrier Category	Specific Barriers
Costs	<p>Training time Lost production time Money (financial investment) Individuals paying out of own pocket</p> <p>Resources (e.g. Space constraints, Equipment availability, Software and subscriptions)</p>
Effectiveness	<p>Why bother? Questioning value / ROI Difficulties measuring benefits Limited understanding of possibilities/ ability to imagine potential</p>
Simplicity	<p>Not particularly easy or quick to understand /learn Lack of competence with tech generally Requires extensive training Ongoing learning as software changes</p>
Compatibility	<p>Seen as conflicting with costume craft practices and values Conservatism/resistance among peers Fear (of change, future or job losses) Desire to work physically / offline</p>
Observability	<p>Part of build process, not visible on stage Requires exposure in workrooms</p>

Appendix 9: Analysis Codebook

Barrier Category	Specific Barriers
	Awaiting others' proof-of-concept
Trialability	Understanding when and how to test out Limited opportunities for experimentation
Sustainability	Environmental costs of technology Energy consumption concerns Material waste in testing and production

4.2 Enablers to Adoption

Enabler Category	Specific Enablers
Cost	Grants and funds available to support adoption Perceived time savings from use Perceived money /resource savings from use Prices coming down
Effectiveness	Demonstrated productivity gains Quality improvements in outputs Fun
Compatibility	Constant learning seen as part of the work Professional development expectations Technology framed as extension of craft skills
Observability	Practitioners very willing to share knowledge and teach others Desire to move beyond guild model Active online professional communities Demonstration opportunities in workrooms
Trialability	Constantly changing collaborators and projects Variation creates opportunities for experimentation Project-based work structure supports testing
Sustainability	Perceived environmental savings Reduced material waste through digital prototyping Alignment with industry sustainability goals

5. Future-focused Coding: Promises Versus Perils

Adopted from related research in fashion (Gustafsson et al., 2025), a dialectical framework considered the implications, contradictions and tensions in technology adoption:

Promises of Adoption	Perils of Adoption
Sustainability through reduced sampling and material waste	Sustainable only if intentionally implemented; can lead to overflow of production or sampling

Appendix 9: Analysis Codebook

Promises of Adoption	Perils of Adoption
Efficiency and optimisation of design and production processes	Efficiency used to cut labour costs and employment opportunities
Upskilling and reskilling opportunities	Talent pipeline disruptions
Alternative income streams realised (training, digital sales)	Outsourcing of work to cheaper labour pools
Facilitating communication and collaboration	Intellectual property lost or stolen
High-fidelity prototyping	High-fidelity prototyping prevents material discoveries
Open-source and sharing culture adopted from other domains	Knowledge democratisation leads to devaluing professional work

6. Coding Validation Processes

The codebook was developed iteratively through multiple passes:

- **Initial code generation:** Codes generated from subset of transcripts
- **Systematic application:** Refined codes applied across full dataset
- **Documentation:** Code definitions documented with inclusion and exclusion criteria and exemplar quotes